

May 1, 2025

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International scientific and practical conference. International scientific and Applied Research. 10.05.2025.

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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FITOREMEDIATSIYA-O‘SIMLIKLAR ORQALI EKOLOGIK MUHITNI TOZALASH

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Annotatsiya: Hozirgi intensiv qishloq xo‘jaligi amaliyotlari va sanoatlashtirish sharoitida er va suv kabi tabiiy resurslarning og‘ir metallar, organik ifloslantiruvchi moddalar, radionuklidlar, pestitsidlar va o‘g‘itlar bilan ifloslanishi katta tashvishga aylandi. Fitoremediatsiya - bu turli manbalardan atrof-muhitga chiqariladigan birikmalarni harakatsizlantirish, o‘zlashtirish, toksikligini kamaytirish, barqarorlashtirish yoki degradatsiya qilish uchun o‘simliklardan foydalanadigan tejamkor va ekologik toza usul. Fitoremediatsiyaning arzonligi va o‘simliklar va qayta tiklanadigan energiyadan foydalanish bilan bog‘liq barqarorlikni hisobga olgan holda, fitoremediatsiya tuproq va suvni organik va noorganik ifloslantiruvchi moddalardan barqaror va iqtisodiy tozalash uchun ishonchli yechim bo‘lishi mumkin.

Kalit so‘zlar: Ifloslantiruvchi moddalar; Tuproq va suvni qayta ishlash; ; O‘simliklarga asoslangan texnologiya

Turli xil organik ifloslantiruvchi moddalar orasida xlorli erituvchilar, neft uglevodorodlari portlovchi moddalari, poliklorli bifenillar (PCB), polisiklik aromatik uglevodorodlar (PAH), piren va trinitrotoluol (TNT) asosiy moddalardir. Tuproqni tez-tez ifloslantiradigan pestitsidlar orasida atrazin , dieldrin , geksaxlorbenzol , diklorodifeniltrixloretan (DDT) va 1,2,4-triklorbenzol . Bu ifloslantiruvchi moddalar tuproqda uzoq vaqt saqlanishi va zaharliligi tufayli tuproq biotasiga , mineral ozuqalar mavjudligiga va tuproq unumdorligiga jiddiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi .[1-2-3]

Tuproqlar singari, suv resurslari ham turli ifloslantiruvchi moddalar bilan ifloslangan. Urbanizatsiya va sanoatlashtirish faoliyati kanalizatsiya, oqava suvlar va oqava suvlar orqali zaharli og‘ir metallarni chiqaradi, bu suvning ifloslanishi omillarining katta qismini tashkil qiladi.[4]

Fitoremediatsiya ifloslangan tuproq va suvdan ifloslantiruvchi moddalarni o‘z ichiga olish, ajratish yoki zararsizlantirish uchun yashil o‘simliklardan foydalanadi. U ifloslantiruvchi moddalarni parchalash, olib tashlash yoki immobilizatsiya qilish uchun degradatsiya (rizo-degradatsiya, fitodegradatsiya), to‘plash (fitoekstraksiya, rizofiltratsiya), dissipatsiya (fitovolatilizatsiya) va immobilizatsiya (gidravlik nazorat va fitostabilizatsiya) kabi ko‘plab mexanizmlardan foydalanadi.[5]

Remediatsiyaga ildiz yoki rizoferada toksik moddalar yoki ifloslantiruvchi moddalarni inaktivatsiya yoki immobilizatsiya qilish orqali erishish mumkin . O‘simlik ildizlarining barqarorlashtiruvchi faolligi ifloslantiruvchi moddalarning

harakatchanligini va biologik mavjudligini cheklaydi, bu esa toksik ta'sirni kamaytiradi. Ba'zi o'simliklar zaharli ifloslantiruvchi moddalarning bog'langan qoldiqlarini hosil qiladi, ular zaharli shaklda mavjud emas yoki to'planganidan keyin qattiq matritsadan ajralib chiqa olmaydi. Misol uchun, *Ryegrass* o'simligi *trifluralin gerbitsidini* qabul qilishi va uni bog'langan qoldiqga aylantirishi mumkin. O'simliklarni to'g'ri tanlash orqali har bir fitoremediatsiya mexanizmining hissasini maksimal darajada oshirish mumkin va fitoremediatsiya texnologiyasi samaradorligini yanada oshirish yo'llari haqida to'liq ma'lumotlar hali ham mavjud emas.[6]

Fitoremediatsiya uchun foydali o'simliklar: *Gorchitsa* (*Brassica juncea*) - og'ir metallarga boy tuproqlarni tozalashda samarali. *O'rik daraxti* (*Populus spp.*)- sanoat chiqindilari bilan ifloslangan hududlarni tozalash uchun ishlatiladi. *Kanop* (*Cannabis sativa*) - og'ir metallarni o'zlashtirish qobiliyatiga ega. *Kungaboqar* (*Helianthus annuus*)-neft va kimyoviy moddalar bilan ifloslangan tuproqni tiklashda yordam beradi. *Suv giatsinti* (*Eichhornia crassipes*)- suv havzalarini og'ir metall va pestitsidlardan tozalash uchun ishlatiladi.[7]

Xulosa

Fitoremediatsiya tabiiy, arzon va barqaror usul ekanligida bo'lsa-da, uzoq vaqt talab qilishi va faqat ma'lum sharoitlarda samarali ishlashi kabi cheklovlari ham mavjud. Ushbu yondashuv ekologik muammolarni hal qilishda innovatsion va istiqbolli usul bo'lib, barqaror rivojlanish tamoyillariga mos keladi. Kelajakda genetik modifikatsiyalangan o'simliklar va ilg'or biotexnologik usullar yordamida fitoremediatsiyaning samaradorligini oshirish mumkin.

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